

THE ROLE OF LITERARY TEXT IN TEACHING RUSSIAN AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Nowadays, reading occupies an important place in the life of every modern person. Through reading, we gain new knowledge, get to know the world around us more deeply. Books develop a person and have an impact on his feelings and thoughts. Thus, reading is an important and integral part of human life. If we talk about modernity, then people are increasingly interested in reading texts in a foreign language [1]. And this is due not only to the fact that people need it for work, for business negotiations, but learning another language through reading is a very exciting and interesting job, which is one of the important stages in learning a foreign language. To accomplish this task, teachers who specialize in teaching a language as a foreign language come to the aid of students. Russian literature in teaching the Russian language for foreigners will be considered in this article.

How it was already mentioned, the literary text plays an important role in the RFL teaching system. Considering the question of the goals and objectives of teaching Russian as a foreign language, we can note several points. Therefore, the main task of an RFL teacher is to teach students the norms, rules, and the language being studied, which include 4 levels of speech activity: listening, reading, writing, and speaking [2]. However, to communicate fluently in Russian, it is not enough to know the rules of this language, syntax, grammar, or just learn words. This is also important, of course, but it is necessary to get acquainted with Russian culture, everyday life, and customs. And it is with the help of fiction that we can get a lot of information, learn about the country, famous people, writers, composers, and artists [**Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.**].

Therefore, another important task that the teacher faces is to familiarize students with the culture of the language being studied and the features associated with it. Therefore, in solving this problem, artistic texts come to our aid, through which we more easily understand the culture of foreign language, and country. So, for example, reading Ostrovsky's plays, you can find out what the merchants were in Russia in that time, or how people lived and what their conversations were about. Reading Tolstoy's «War and Peace», in addition to the stories of human destinies, we learn about important events during which the action of the novel unfolds - this is the war of 1812.

Of course, there are many stylistic, phraseological, grammatical elements in fiction, various expressive means such as tropes, or metaphors and comparisons. In addition, the language of literature can include slangs, dialectisms, colloquialisms, which, of course, is difficult to understand not only for a foreign student, but also sometimes for a person for whom this language is native [**Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.**].

Therefore, when a student works with a text, it is assumed that he understands it holistically, can navigate it, highlight the main idea. In this regard, the teacher chooses the assignments for the student. There are pre-text, pre-text and post-text tasks [**Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.**].

The main task of the pre-text tasks is introductory work. Here we learn information about the author, about the work, and the teacher introduces students to the vocabulary of this text, gives the meaning of incomprehensible words and expressions. At the next, pre-textual stage, it is important to help students in reading the text, to help them imagine the general situation of the text and apply new words that students learned at the first stage.

When reading the first texts, it is also important to ask leading questions - this further helps students to independently see the problem and analyze the text. During the actual work, you can use color painting. This is a technique that helps to understand the work more deeply, for example, to correlate color and some event or image of the hero [**Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.**]. So, in the

work of F.M. Dostoevsky there is a lot of yellow color, which many researchers interpret as a symbol of "poverty" and "suffering". In a literary text, every word, sign means something. The teacher invites students to present these details, describe them, and describe the gestures of the characters, their appearance and actions.

Well, the last stage is the post-text one. Here, all two stages are connected together and the result is summed up. The teacher checks the students' knowledge of understanding the text, asks them to tell the content of the text, the statements of critics, and so on [**Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.**].

In addition, well-chosen texts increase students' motivation. Boring and difficult texts will not be interesting, therefore, especially at the initial stages, they should not be very large and complex works, you can start, for example, with stories by A.P. Chekhov, A.S. Pushkin, N.V. Gogol.

The most effective way is to conduct lessons interactively, giving group assignments, discuss texts, hold games or arrange debates. You can do theatrical performances from the works, so that the information is easier to remember, students will be able to analyze the text and understand it better [**Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.**]. Another interesting feature is the comparison of works in Russian with the foreign works, which is written in their native language. This task will allow you to better understand the difference between the two languages, to see the similarities and differences [**Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.**].

Russian literature education in the framework of learning Russian as a foreign language helps students not only to learn the language, but also to better understand the culture and society of Russia through literary works. When creating a Russian literature course for students from other countries, it is important to take into account various aspects and strive to make the program flexible, appropriate to the level of training and cultural characteristics of students.

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